

JOB DEMAND AND ITS IMPACT ON TURNOVER INTENTIONS DURING COVID 19 CRISIS

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ABSTRACT

An in-depth review of current human resources policies, processes, documentary evidence, and systems is performed in order to identify areas for improvement and augmentation of the HR function, as well as to ensure compliance with constantly changing rules and regulations. Workforce diversity is a suitable technique (or means) of evaluating current human resources policies, procedures, documentation and systems in order to identify areas for development and betterment of the HR function, as well as to ensure compliance with constantly changing and dynamic. A job rotation entails doing a systematic examination of all elements of human resources, which is often done in a checklist format. Main goal of the research is to investigate the various sectors of the human resources department and to offer a new HR philosophy to support the HR activities of the firms during the period of the Covid. For this aim, a sample of 150 respondents was drawn from the pool, and it is concluded that, the employees can understand the firm's strengths and weaknesses, as well as to examine their employee's standards which includes examining policies and strategies, hiring people, keeping the most productive employees, and giving training, among other things.

Keywords: Job demand, Turnover intention and Covid 19.

1.0 INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY

Human resource management (HRM) comprises a variety of responsibilities such as human resource planning, workforce planning, recruiting, screening, induction, performance appraisal, safety and health, welfare, and industrial relations, among others. These responsibilities are carried out in order to achieve certain social, functional, and personal goals.

The HR Job Rotation process is a method of analysing policies, processes, records, systems, and practices related to a firm's HR activities in order to make improvements. Work rotation is intended to expose the strengths and weaknesses of the charity's human resources system, as well as any concerns that need to be addressed. The job rotation strategy works best when the emphasis is on examining and enhancing the hr functions in the company, as it is in this case. Job rotation is a diagnostic tool rather than a normative instrument, as is the case with most other instruments. It will assist you in identifying what you are lacking or something you need to improve upon, but it will not tell you what you need to do in order to solve these concerns. If an organisation is ready to act on the results and develop its human resources function to the point where it can fully support the business's goal and objectives, this kind of research is most beneficial.

Meaning of job rotation:

Job rotation is very beneficial in achieving an organization's purpose, and it is also an important tool in evaluating the success of an organization's human resource management activities.

Approaches to job rotation:

- There are five ways that may be used to evaluate human resource performance in any organisation:
- Taking a qualitative methodology
- External control; statistical analysis; a compliance-oriented strategy; and management by objectives
- Management By Objectives(MBO)

Employee turnover:

It relates to the procedure through which workers leave their respective firms. A higher turnover rate entails a higher cost for recruiting, selection, training, and other related activities. A high turnover rate might also result in production interruptions, quality control issues, and other challenges. Labor turnover is inevitable and includes resignations, retirements, deaths, and transfers. Improved recruiting methods, orientation and training, working conditions, better compensation, and development opportunities are some of the particular activities that may be taken to lower employee turnover levels.

2.0 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

As the demand towards job is getting increased due to pandemic situation and lack of employees, the demand towards employees got increased in recent days which lead to increase in employee demand in recent days. Thus the following factors are taken as problem towards the study,

- What is the perception of employees towards different sectors of HR during the pandemic situation?
- What the various attributes contribute towards HR department of the companies?

3.0 OBJECTIVES

- To study the different sectors of the HR department during covid 19.
- To analyze the various functional attributes of the HR department

4.0 SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

- During Covid, the study was limited to just the personnel of the firms that participated.
- As a result of the project being done on a small number of samples from a constrained set of conditions, there will be a great deal of confidence in the firms during Covid.

- The information gathered will be of the greatest use to the firms during Covid, and the recommendations will provide them with fresh ideas for dealing with their staff.
- The personnel are really receptive to the questions we pose to them. As a result, the senior management of the organisations participating in Covid will have excellent access to data for analysis and interpretation.

5.0 NEED FOR THE STUDY:

- Job rotation is extremely important for companies during Covid because the psychological behaviour of each and every employee has an impact on the productivity of the company.
- Companies currently should analyse their human resource policies on a regular basis, and after analysing the factors, they should make regular updates.
- Job rotation is a significant tool that firms may utilise during Covid to bring in new blood and keep it flowing throughout the organisation.

6.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design: The study is descriptive in nature.

Sampling Design & Tools Applied

Sampling techniques

Sampling Unit: During Covid, the sampling unit may be characterized as the fundamental unit that contains the job rotation towards the many enterprises.

Sampling Size: The sample size for this study is one hundred and fifty people, who were chosen from among the workers of the firms participating in the Covid conference.

Sampling Type: In this study, convenience sampling has been modified to meet the needs of the participants. In addition, the following statistical tools are used: (a) the chi-square test, (b) the percentage analysis, and (c) the rank correlation.

7.0 DATA COLLECTION

Primary data: During Covid, the main data from the respondents, which was obtained via a questionnaire schedule, was utilized with personnel from the participating organizations.

Secondary data: Secondary data was gathered from firms throughout the Covid profile process, as well as from instructions, publications, periodicals, and periodicals, among other sources.

8.0 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The scope of the research is confined to respondents who were chosen from inside and around Coimbatore, and the sample unit was also limited to 150 respondents, which means that the results might be incorrect.

9.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Demographic factors

	Particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Gender	Male	91	60.7
	Female	59	39.3
	Total	150	100
Age	20-25 years	35	23.3
	26-30 years	46	30.7
	31-35years	30	20
	36-40 years	24	16
	Above 41 years	15	10
Educational qualification	12th	45	30
	UG	54	36
	PG	27	18
	Others	24	16
	Total	150	100

Among the participants, 60.7 percent are male and the other 39.3 percent are female, for a total of 150 respondents. 20% of participants are between the ages of 20 and 25 years, 30.7 percent are between the ages of 26 and 30, 20 percent are between the ages of 31 and 35, 16 percent are between the ages of 36 and 40, and 10% are beyond the age of 41. 30% of those who answered the survey studied 12th grade, 36 percent finished an UG degree, 18 percent obtained a PG degree, and 16 percent belonged to the other group.

Respondent's opinion on timeframe of conducting training program

Particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Once in a month	55	36.7
Quarterly	46	30.7
Half yearly	26	17.3
Annually	23	15.3
Total	150	100.0

The respondents' thoughts on the timeline for implementing the training programme. 36.7 percent of those who responded say they do it once a month, 30.7 percent say they do so quarterly, 17.3 percent say they do so half yearly, and 15.3 percent say they do so annually.

Opinion on mode of recruitment process involved in the organisation during covid

Particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Through agencies	40	26.7
Through employee reference	35	23.3
Through advertisement	45	30.0
Through colleges	30	20.0
Total	150	100.0

26.7 percent of those who responded say they found jobs via agencies, 23.3 percent say they found jobs through employee references, 30 percent say they found jobs through advertisements, and 20 percent say they found jobs through universities.

Opinion on companies adapting to internal factors during covid

Particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Transfer	64	42.7
Promotion	55	36.7
Demotion	24	16.0
Others	7	4.7
Total	150	100.0

During Covid, the corporations were responding to their own internal causes. 42.7 percent of them believe that transfer is the best option, 36.7 percent believe that promotion is the best option, 16 percent believe that demotion is the best option, and 4.7 percent believe that others are the best options.

Person in strategic job rotation

Particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
General manager	46	30.7
Production manager	38	25.3
HR manager	58	38.7
Job rotation	8	5.3
Total	150	100.0

The individuals involved in job redesign are listed in the table above. In answer to this question, 30.7 percent of them indicate general manager, 25.3 percent say production manager, 38.7 percent say human resources manager, and 5.3 percent cite job rotation as their response.

Time period of conducting job rotation

Particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Once in a year	64	42.7
Twice	55	36.7
Once in three months	24	16.0
Others	7	4.7
Total	150	100.0

42.7 percent say they do it once a year, 36.7 percent say they do it twice a year, 16 percent say they do it once every three months, and 4.7 percent say they do it other times.

Incentives and allowances procedure in the organisations

Particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Productivity linked	55	36.7
Performance based pay	29	19.3
Profit incentives	27	18.0
Stock opinion	22	14.7
Retirement benefit	17	11.3
Total	150	100.0

36.7 percent of respondents say it is based on productivity linked pay, 19.3 percent say it is premised on performance bonuses, 18 percent percent say it is based on profit incentives, 14.7 percent say it is based on share price opinion, and 11.3 percent say it is based on retirement pension as their answer.

Age of the respondents * opinion on employees achieving goals and targets during covid

H0: Age of the employees have no relation on their opinion on achieving goals and targets

Crosstab							
Count							
		Opinion on employees achieving goals and targets					Total
		Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
Age of the respondents	20-25 years	18	7	3	6	1	35
	26-30 years	15	13	5	5	8	46
	31-35years	11	7	7	3	2	30
	36-40 years	11	4	4	3	2	24
	Above 41 years	5	4	2	2	2	15
Total		60	35	21	19	15	150

Sig= 0.733 No relation exists between age (0.733) and opinion on employees achieving goals and targets.

Comparison between age of and perception of employees on various factors related to Job rotation during Covid

Model Summary	
R	R Square
.244 ^a	.059

It reveals that moderate relation exists between the compared variables.

Coefficients ^a						
Variables		Un-Cof		S-Cof	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1		3.503	.338		10.356	.000
	Opinion on satisfaction level selection process involved	-.209	.088	-.190	-2.367	.019
	Opinion on companies during Covid-adopting to internal factors	-.176	.119	-.119	-1.474	.143
	Opinion on companies during Covid-source with external factors	-.063	.073	-.069	-.861	.391
a. Dependent Variable: Age of the respondents						

Age of the respondents (Constant) 3.503= Opinion on satisfaction level selection process involved (-0.209)+ Opinion on companies during Covid adopting to internal factors (-.176) + Opinion on companies during Covid source with external factors (0.063).

Rank Correlation

S.NO	Ranking	X	Y	R1	R2	D	D ²
1	Financial incentives	4	6	6	6.5	-0.5	0.25
2	Financial allowances	3	6	7	6.5	0.5	0.25
3	Job rotation	8	11	5	5	0	0.00
4	Job enrichment	26	31	2	2	0	0.00
5	Job security	49	62	1	1	0	0.00
6	Performance appraisal	11	28	4	3	1	1.00
7	Job control	29	17	3	4	-1	1.00
							2.50
N	7					1-R	0.04
	.					R	0.96

The correlation is at 0.96 which shows that the ranks given are highly correlated and the priority was given to Job security.

10.0 FINDINGS

- The majority of them (30 percent) claim they found out about it via advertising.
- The majority of respondents (38.7%) were very happy with the selecting process.
- Of the 150 respondents, 42.7% believe that transfer is adopted as a result of internal considerations.
- The majority of them (36.7 percent) claim they were recruited via a campus interview.
- The majority of respondents (46 percent) believe that formal culture is followed in the firms.
- A large majority of respondents (60.7 percent) believe that employees should get initial training before being placed on the job.
- Work rotation and job enrichment are mentioned by 68 percent of those who answered the survey questions.

11.0 SUGGESTIONS

- The companies should not be hesitant to invest money on educating their personnel since training allows them to contribute more to the well-being of the business while also improving their own talents at the same time.

- A greater weekly meeting can be held in which the opinions of employees should be recognised since the satisfaction of employees is critical to the growth of the organisations.
- The recruitment process should be strengthened in order to acquire the most potential people for the most appropriate positions. Campus discussions can be used to lower the cost of recruitment for the organisations.

12.0 CONCLUSION

The conclusion is that the employees can understand the firm's strengths and weaknesses, as well as to examine their employee's standards which includes examining policies and strategies, hiring people, keeping the most productive employees, and giving training, among other things.

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